

VULNERABILITY TO VIABILITY
GLOBAL PARTNERSHIP

Motivations as Drivers Behind Conservation Transformations: Reflections from the Chilika - V2V Field School

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V2V Working Paper Series

V2V Global Partnership “Working Paper Series” aims to facilitate the exchange of ideas, mobilize knowledge, and generate broad-based discussions on vulnerability-viability themes within the context of small-scale fisheries. The Working Paper Series will provide a collaborative and interactive platform for academics, practitioners, representatives of civil society, and individuals interested in making written contributions to the theoretical, methodological, practical, and policy aspects of small-scale fisheries, both locally and globally. To contribute to the V2V Working Paper Series, please contact v2vglobalpartnership@gmail.com.

Reflections from Chilika - V2V Field School

Small-scale fisheries (SSF) are important social-ecological systems across all parts of the world. Strongly anchored in local communities, SSFs reflect a way of life, and they provide critical contributions. Yet, their efforts and their existence are often overlooked as many SSF communities remain economically and politically marginalized, are highly vulnerable to change, and remain invisible in policy debates. Nonetheless, the continuity of many SSFs suggests certain strengths and forms of resilience. A holistic understanding of what causes vulnerability, as well as what makes fisheries social-ecological systems viable and through what processes is required. This understanding needs to be place-based and situated within the SSF context, and the processes surrounding it must be long-term, collaborative and iterative.

The Chilika - V2V Field School aims to provide a creative platform for graduate students and early career scholars and practitioners to deliberate and learn about concepts, approaches and methods helpful to achieving transitions from vulnerability to viability within SSF social-ecological systems. The Field School takes place every year in the Chilika Lagoon, Bay of Bengal, India, where participants gain firsthand experience and creatively engage in furthering their understanding and knowledge of vulnerability to viability transitions, and experiment with concepts and approaches that are novel, transdisciplinary and problem oriented. The Reflections from Chilika - V2V Field School is part of the V2V Working Paper Series that exclusively focuses on documenting the main learnings, insights, reflections gained by the Chilika - V2V Field School participants during their weeklong journey with the fisher communities of Chilika Lagoon.

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Motivations as Drivers Behind Conservation Transformations: Reflections from the Chilika - V2V Field School

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Abstract

This reflection paper was written by a diverse group of learners from Indonesia, India, and Canada and focuses on the key drivers shaping community-based conservation in Odisha. Drivers, in this context, refer to the motivations that inspired communities to move towards conserving their environments across three central categories: (a) Preserving a Sense of Community, (b) Response to Existing Threats and Vulnerabilities, and (c) Response to Anticipated Future Threats. The project draws on three specific cases based on field visits by the authors - Mangalajodi (adjacent to Chilika Lagoon) known for its transition to eco-tourism, the coastal communities of Ganjam district, and the forested village of Uparadikiri. Early sections include field observations with descriptions, photovoice, a table of sensory experiences from each site, and poems. For example, in Ganjam, observations note meetings with village elders in the community mandir, a mural depicting turtles to highlight ecological change, and sensory elements like sea sand and breaking waves; poems also explore themes of change, including an erasure poem from field notes and a poem from the perspective of nesting turtles. Additional sections detail our data collection methods, reflections, abstract conceptualization, and discussion. Reflections examine the three drivers across all sites, noting, for instance, how the Wildlife Protection Act of 1972 influenced eco-tourism in Mangalajodi and how the *Chuli-Chanda* Forest protection system reflects community preservation in Uparadikiri. Conceptual frameworks such as Maslow's hierarchy of needs and ecopsychology support the analysis by linking community well-being with environmental health. The discussion synthesizes insights across all cases, showing how preserving a sense of community emerged consistently—from coastal mapping to communal prayers—while responses to existing and anticipated threats were shaped by legal regulations (e.g., coastal zone rules and the Wildlife Protection Act) and by community actions ranging from eco-tourism development to mango nursery initiatives.

Keywords Community-based conservation • Experiential learning • Sense of community • Environmental vulnerability • Eco-tourism • Participatory methods

1. Introduction

The reflections presented in this paper emerge from a learning experience conducted as part of the Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Chilika Annual Field School 2025. This paper focuses on the drivers of changes observed for community-based conservation in Odisha, and particularly in the socio-ecological system across the Chilika lagoon and its neighbouring landscapes.

Chilika is one of the largest brackish water lagoons in Asia, situated along India's east coast. Bordered by the Bay of Bengal to the south and the Eastern Ghats stretching across the northern and western catchments, the lagoon extends across three districts of Odisha – Puri, Khordha, and Ganjam. The wetland covers a maximum area of 1165 km² during the monsoon season. Being a rich biodiversity hotspot, it was recognised as a Ramsar Site in 1981, under the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands. It is one of the largest wintering grounds for migratory birds along the Central and East Asian Australasian Flyway, hosting around 225 bird species at its peak season, and is also home to the Irrawaddy dolphin (*Orcaella brevirostris*). The lagoon sustains a highly productive fishery, supporting the livelihoods of more than 400,000 fishers and their families across over 150 villages.

Over the years, the lagoon and neighbouring landscapes have seen significant transformations and faced several challenges particularly since the 1990s due to natural causes as well as human activities. Two prominent changes were the growth of shrimp aquaculture in the 1980s and the opening of an artificial sea mouth to the Bay of Bengal in 2001. The former sparked debates over rights of access and resource use, with non-fishing communities entering the fishery, while the latter triggered biophysical changes that affected the livelihoods of many dependent households.

While the changes could either be positive or negative for the lagoon's ecology and community well-being, it is essential to understand what factors drove these changes within such a complex system, in order to further assess the adaptive strategies that have emerged in response. This paper focuses on conservation-related transitions observed during fieldwork, analysing the underlying drivers that shaped these developments. While we recognise that various ecological and socio-economic factors could demand the adoption of conservation strategies in these regions, this paper particularly emphasizes the behavioural motivations of communities as critical drivers of transformative change.

Preservation-focused community transformation is not a one-off occurrence, but rather a group reaction based on common goals that act as potent change agents. When communities are faced with the need to protect their social, cultural, or environmental resources, the motivational frameworks that inspire group action are essentially what propel sustainable change. These incentives function as dynamic catalysts, transforming personal worries into concerted community-wide initiatives that go beyond conventional limits of participation.

2. Process of experiential learning

As part of this experiential learning across the Chilika lagoon, we explored drivers of change through the lens of community resilience, wellbeing, and conservation. Given the scope of the field school, our insights are based on reflective observations and informal conversations. The reflections presented here are therefore exploratory and not conclusive. Additionally, the immersive nature of this learning experience adds to the depth of understanding the context.

2.1 Field visits:

This paper draws insights from three major field visits, where we observed conservation-oriented changes emerging from community responses to pressures and vulnerabilities.

The three regions focused on this study include the Mangalajodi wetland sanctuary, villages in Ganjam and the Uparadikiri forest village.

Mangalajodi is a village in the Khordha district of Odisha, located on the northern end of Chilika Lagoon. Known for its scenic wetlands, it became a separate Grama Panchayat in 2017. These wetlands attract over 150,000 migratory birds from around the world during the peak season. Recognized as an International Bird Conservation Area, Mangalajodi is now a prominent community-managed bird sanctuary.

Ganjam is the southernmost district of Odisha, with 27 coastal villages and the highest number of landing centres and non-motorised fishing crafts in the state, emphasizing its strong traditional fishing culture. The region's economy is highly dependent on fishing. The Chilika lagoon runs parallel to this district in the northeast to southwest direction. The region is also known for a spectacular phenomenon – the mass nesting of Olive Ridley Turtles, near the Rushikulya river (that flows directly into the Bay of Bengal) mouth in the district.

Uparadikiri is a village located in Daspalla tehsil in the Nayagarh district of Odisha. The region is a forest range characterised by diverse flora and fauna, and the lives of the community are rooted in local and traditional knowledge and practices.

2.2 Immersive experience and reflective observations:

The reflections we gathered are primarily based on the responses we received through the interactions with community members, local organisers, and key stakeholders. These conversations were complemented by participant observation of the local context and practices. Along this process, field observation notes were carefully made and, later, a thematic analysis was conducted by the team to arrive at a theoretical framework to conceptualise our learnings.

At each site, we:

1. Identified a major conservation-related change (e.g., community commons mapping in Ganjam).
2. Backtracked the sequence of events, issues, and pressure points leading to the change.
3. Interpreted community responses as being shaped by underlying behavioural motivations.
4. Categorised these motivations into three broad variables emerging across sites:
 - Preserving a sense of community (identity, ownership, belonging)
 - Response to existing threats and vulnerabilities (livelihood loss, displacement)
 - Response to anticipated future threats (future risks, preparedness, resilience-building)

2.3 Cross-site comparison

As final reflections, the paper draws on findings from all three sites to explore patterns of motivations as drivers of change. By situating motivations within the broader conservation transformations observed, we reflect on how they could potentially contribute to resilience, wellbeing, and collective action.

3. Field Observations

For all three selected locations for this report (Mangalajodi, Ganjam District and Uparadikiri), field observations shared include four main components. These are:

- A brief description of the group visit itself in a narrative format (component I),
- Multiple photos taken that symbolically captures both the experience and the project theme focusing on drivers known as photovoice (component II),
- A table showing various non-visual site observations based on the other senses (e.g. smell, feel) to both allow for a sense of immersion for the reader and second, to acknowledge that sight alone can be limiting as a tool (component III),
- Poetry written about project themes at each site (component IV).

3.1 Narrative Observations

Site 1: Mangalajodi

The authors visited Mangalajodi (a birding sanctuary) on a sunny, hot, and humid August morning. We arrived at the launch site following an auto-rickshaw journey and were greeted by large, colourful signs showing potential bird species to see in the wetland - including many from far away such as Siberia.

What followed was a lovely expedition into the wetlands by small wooden boats with a captain (navigating with a wooden pole) and an extremely knowledgeable guide who showed us various species we spotted, like herons, in an informational birding book. The journey lasted about an hour as the boats traversed a grassy, marshy landscape interspersed with bird eggs, water buffaloes, motorized boats, and countless wetland grasses. Bird sightings were rare as many migratory birds primarily visit Odisha in the winter months which is peak visitor season compared to the quieter summer months (based on our guide).

Conservations gleaned by several teammates (Tapas and Deeksha) with the guides noted that before this eco-tourism initiative was established two and a half decades ago, the villagers of Mangalajodi had a more complicated relationship with the surrounding physical environment including engaging in extensive bird and fish poaching. Currently, the community is focused on eco-tourism and has what they described as a more symbiotic relationship with nature.

Site 2: Ganjam District

Later, in our visit to Chilika at the southern end of the lagoon along the Bay of Bengal, our group visited two nearby coastal communities in the Ganjam District which were very different and similar at the same time.

- Community 1 had a very unfortunate physical geographic setting. The small village was located on a steep degrading cliff above a rapidly eroding beach and the group observed that many homes directly next to the cliff were abandoned. At the site we descended onto the beach and felt the rough reddish sand and wet waves. Afterward, the group had a thoughtful and sad discussion with a local guide and scholar. He suggested many reasons for why the village was experiencing erosion and was partially abandoned from greater rainfall to sand mining (and changes in sedimentation) to cyclones. He also lamented that the beach once hosted many turtles when it was longer.
- The second community had a different feeling despite experiencing similar impacts such as erosion. When we arrived, several village men were preparing a large meal chopping vegetables such as onions. We were ushered into the village mandir and had a long discussion with three community leaders who spoke incredibly passionately about how they tackled land and fishing rights issues to protect their

village. The centrepiece of this push was a community mapping process based on Coastal Regulation Zones which they explained is unique in the Indian rural context. The three leaders also spoke about change and how before the community mapping, the community faced pressing issues such as encroachment which still exist but have lessened. Additionally, they concurred with many of the driving forces noted by the guide at Site 1 such as cyclones which can impede the ability to fish. After the dialogue, we ventured south to the river mouth, a complex coastal landscape with islands and different bodies of water. There, we saw a group of villagers collecting juvenile shrimp to use in aquaculture which was quite interesting to observe (i.e. tiny black specks swimming in containers of water).

Site 3: Uparadikiri

Uparadikiri is a bit different from the other two sites and is located ~100 kilometres northwest of Chilika in a mountainous setting away from a large body of water. This was our group's last community visit, and we visited on a misty, drizzling day. What stood out to our group was the extreme kindness of the villagers who warmly greeted us in many ways from creating a mural, to dancing, to providing bouquets and lemon water in banana leaves. The introduction also included a discussion of how the villagers worked to protect their forest rights from encroachment and illegal logging several years ago which helped the forest ecosystem replenish.

Following the village introduction, were three additional parts of the visit.

- *Component 1:* First our group walked through the Uparadikiri community forest. Here we learned about medicinal plants and an agroforestry initiative growing mango trees.
- *Component 2:* The second part involved a delicious village lunch. On the way Alex was followed by a sweet village dog. The meal was extremely generous and included local produce and livestock with dishes such as roasted eggplant and chicken curry. It was served on a stone platform atop banana leaves and communal. Scraps were shared with village dogs afterwards.
- *Component 3:* The final component was a discussion with village leaders about the impetus for forest protection. Three important points were noted throughout this process. First was the Tengah Pali system (a project that empowers various villagers to directly monitor their forest). The second was the role of Gram Sabha, a council system to deal with disputes. The third is the role of women who are empowered in community action and conversation.

3.2 Photovoice Observations

Site 1: Mangalajodi

One photo that exemplifies the group project theme is a picture of a gorgeous purplish water lily picked by a Mangalajodi tour guide and shared with Alex and Deeksha (Figure 1). The wetland is filled with them, and they come in many different hues from purple to pink to white. The guide told us local villagers often consume the stem as well. Personally, this flower symbolizes the idea of behavioural change quite well as it highlights a changing relationship with the natural world for many of these boat guides and captains when poaching was widespread and versus now. It also ties into the idea of ecological change as based on conversation before the boat tour initiative; the wetland landscape was less lush.

Figure 1

Photo of a purple water lily picked by the Mangalajodi tour guide in the wetland and shared with the group

Site 2: Ganjam District

One photo that exemplifies the group theme is Figure 2, a huge turtle mural that was painted in the second community (Pallibandha). It depicts local Olive Ridley turtles swimming in the Bay of Bengal, smiling, which to a viewer evokes images of hope and resilience and a possible future.

Unfortunately, coastal erosion has made it rough for these turtles to find nesting places in the Ganjam district based on resident conversations especially in Community 1 and their protection was part of the push for conservation and community mapping in Community 2.

Figure 2

Olive Ridley Turtle mural in Pallibandha (Community 2)

Site 3: Uparadikiri

One visual that encapsulates both the village visit for our group and the idea of change is a local man with a cane and hat, charged with forest protection under the Tengah Pali system (Figure 3a). Forest protection is the responsibility of all villagers and rotates among them.

Figure 3a

Villager wearing a specific hat and holding a bamboo stick charged with the responsibility of forest protection of the Uparadikiri community forest

Another photo below shows an interaction between group member Amiek and a village woman during the initial part of our site visit, where we were given lemon water. This evokes feelings of warmth, camaraderie, and mutual respect (Figure 3b).

Figure 3b

A local villager sharing lemon water with Amiek

3.3. Sensory Observations

Site 1: Mangalajodi

A final set of site observations is concerned with other senses (feel, hear, smell etc.) and how the group experienced them during the visit. These are shown in Table 1 for Mangalajodi.

Table 1	
Observations from other senses at Mangalajodi	
Sense (other than sight)	Observations
Feel	Rough petals of water lilies The smooth feel of the wooden boat
Hear	Water splashing (from buffalo moving through the water) Engines revving from a few nearby motorboats
Smell	A marshy, salty smell (tough to describe) The smell of fish (our group noticed a few fishing boats at the end of the visit processing their catch)
Taste	N/A

Site 2: Ganjam District

See Table 2 for observations on key sensory observations such as the sound of crashing waves at the Ganjam location.

Table 2	
Observations from other senses at Ganjam District	
Sense (other than sight)	Observations
Feel	The gritty sand from the beach
Hear	The sound of waves crashing at the beach The passion in the voices of the three community leaders talking about how they protected their community
Smell	The smell of the sea (salty, briny) In the second community, a wafting delicious smell of food being cooked
Taste	N/A

Site 3: Uparadikiri

Finally, the Uparadikiri visit was an extremely multi-sensory experience. See Table 3.

<i>Table 3</i>	
Observations from other senses at Uparadikiri	
Sense (other than sight)	Observations
Feel	Many different textures particularly during the forest walk including: Rough tree bark, The glossy, smooth feeling of tree leaves,
Hear	The sounds of many local animals include chickens and dogs
Smell	Petrichor: a unique word for the scent of rainy soil See: https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/petrichor
Taste	Numerous thanks to the delicious meal cooked by the villagers and introduction including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The sour-sweet lemon water, • Rich, salty dal with pieces of okra, • Crispy, crunchy papad, • Leafy, bitter local greens • Smoky eggplant

3.4 Poetry Observations

The following section comprises poems based on all three selected locations: Mangalajodi, Ganjam District & Uparadikiri with several poems per each location.

A few important notes on these poems are shared below.

1. They cover a lot of different ideas but build on the central selected theme of ecological and environmental transformation in Chilika and Odisha as well as the idea of drivers and change.
2. These poems are experimental and include a wide array of forms from haikus to erasure poetry; see the detailed glossary by the Poetry Foundation (<https://www.poetryfoundation.org/education/glossary>) for additional information).
3. These poems were based on a mix of observations and conversations with local people and are representative of a small snapshot in time.

I. Mangalajodi***Poem 1:***

*Preserving birds
Preserving fish
Preserving grasses*

Poem 2:

*On my trip to Mangalajodi, I had three random thoughts:
I am not connected to the land or water or sky i live, breathe and sleep on (far different from our boat
guides)
water lilies have extremely long stems
and I forgot the third thought*

Poem 3:

Many clouds

Many buffaloes

Many grasses

II. Ganjam District

Poem 1

*Waves, Waves, Waves, Waves, Waves
Turtles, Turtles, Turtles, Turtles, Turtles, Turtles, Turtles
Maps, Maps, Maps, Maps, Maps*

Poem 2

*Village 1:
Huge erosion
Unpredictable cyclones. Less fish abandoned
feeling of sand mining.
Poor turtle nesting
Less sand dense fixed fishing gears.
Climate change*

*Village 2:
Coastal commons
Long history
Community mapping of the village next generation
fight encroachment and evictions.
Coastal Regulation feeling of empowerment*

Poem 3

*Destructive fishing
Reduction in fish stock
Intense cyclones
Very strong erosion
Enforcement lacking
River mouth migration*

Poem 4

Hopelessness Hopelessness

Hopelessness
Hopelessness Hopelessness
Hopelessness Hopelessness

Poem 5

*Dear Villagers,
Where can we land and nest,
The beach is gone, gone, gone,
So little sand and so much sea,
Are we to disappear?*

*Help us,
Work with us,
Save us,*

*Best,
Olive Ridley Turtles of the Ganjam District*

III. Uparadikiri

Poem 1

I think about the “Woman, Life, Freedom” movement in Iran and realize that the fight for forest rights at Uparadikiri is similar

*Upholding gender equity
Upholding land rights*

*Upholding the right to life***Poem 2**

When I visited Uparadikiri as a foreigner and visitor and outsider I learned two new ideas:

- 1. Thenga Pali (protect the forest internally)*
- 2. Gram Sabah (protect the forest externally)*

Poem 3

*Who hurts the forest? Who hurts the forest? Who hurts the forest?
Who owns the forest? Who owns the forest? Who owns the forest?
Who protects the forest? Who protects the forest? Who protects the forest?*

*The people of Uparadikiri have a right to life and love and laugh.
The trees of Uparadikiri have a right to life and love and laugh.*

Poem 4

*In the Uparadikiri forest:
I smell a tree (wet soil).
I feel a tree (scaly bark).
I hear a tree (chirpy birds).
I taste a tree (sweet, sweet mango).
I see a tree (green leaves).*

4. Reflections**4.1 Mangalajodi****Preserving a Sense of Community**

Bird hunting used to be a big part of everyday life and cultural ceremonies in Mangalajodi, from giving birds as gifts to making sure pregnant women were well. This common tradition created a strong feeling of community identity based on the wetland's riches. When IAS officer N.K. Bhujwal made villagers take a sacred pledge before Mother Kali Jai, he sparked a collective awakening: conservation became a community promise instead of a rule that had to be followed. This spiritual framing brought together former hunters and poachers with a new goal, changing how the community saw itself from being exploiters of the lagoon to being its protectors.

Response to Existing Threats and Vulnerabilities

The Wildlife Protection Act of 1972 made it illegal to hunt without a reason, which led to a decline in bird populations. This was a direct threat to both biodiversity and the livelihoods of people in the area. At first, they didn't want to do it, but they changed their minds when they realized that harming the environment would hurt their own existence. Former poachers became experienced guides who guided bird-watching tours across Chilika's wetlands. They use traditional fishing boats and poles that have been repurposed for eco-tourism to show you nesting platforms, water lilies, different types of fish, and the migrations of

Siberian and native birds. The community converted crisis into strength by turning ecological knowledge into business opportunities. This helped them deal with immediate problems.

Response to Anticipated Future Threats

Mangalajodi has built up its tourism infrastructure in a way that protects the environment while also helping the economy thrive. From November to March, fifty-five boats take thousands of tourists to local homestays and hotels. Most of the money goes to families, some goes to boat upkeep, and the remainder goes to conservation projects in a revenue-sharing scheme. Teaching the next generation these skills will make sure they last. At the same time, the community is still on the lookout for new problems, including more motorboat traffic, that could harm delicate habitats. Their proactive planning and adaptive management show how being ready for future dangers may keep people interested in protecting the environment.

4.2 Uparadikri

Preserving a Sense of Community

Developing a stronger sense of community and shared identity is the cornerstone of this conservation endeavour. With just a stick and a hat, the villagers alternately protect the forest at night, and the *Thengapalli* system is a perfect example of this. By doing this, forest protection is no longer a personal burden but rather a collective community duty. Community solidarity is further strengthened by the "*Chuli-Chanda*" system. Every household makes a financial contribution to the collective forest protection fund, symbolized by their *Chuli* (cookstove). By guaranteeing that each family has a financial interest in conservation initiatives, this strategy fosters social cohesion. Celebrations of culture are also essential to the preservation of communities. Every year, the villagers turn conservation into a festive community event by celebrating biodiversity like a festival. An additional aspect of fostering community is the resuscitation of the "tota system" of communally managed fruit orchards. Village women took charge of maintaining these areas for the benefit of wildlife and future generations by cleaning and sweeping the area to start this revival. The community's conservation efforts gain spiritual depth from their worship of Jagannath, which connects them to their cultural heritage. Since various forest products are used to make the *ratha yatra's* components, protecting forests is both a religious and an environmental necessity.

Response to Existing Threats and Vulnerabilities

Directly confronting current threats is a major source of the community's conservation drive. With loggers methodically removing timber to sell in cities, the wood mafia presented the biggest obstacle. The community's response was forceful; they established distinct territorial claims and used group action to protect their forests. Villagers frequently bribed forest department officials because they were afraid of them prior to the 2005 Forest Rights Act. Communities sought legal recognition of their rights as a result of this vulnerability. To formally assert their claims, they made maps and put up poles announcing who owned the forest. Another major issue was wildfire management, which has gotten worse during the past five years since 2019. To combat this threat, the community created organized forest regulations, going beyond reactive measures to planned preventative measures. Action was also prompted by the deterioration of traditional food systems. Communities realized they urgently needed revival as the fruit forests that once supported villages were destroyed. To recreate the food security that earlier generations experienced, each family now looks after eight trees.

Response to Anticipated Future Threats

Many conservation efforts are motivated by forward-thinking ideas. Concerns about future medical requirements are reflected in the creation of "hathopedi" medicine gardens, which are referred to as the village's jewellery box. The medicinal plants found in these gardens are essential for curing a variety of illnesses, such as vitamin deficiencies and stress-related conditions. Adaptive planning is demonstrated by the bamboo revival project. The community demonstrated their dedication to long-term forest regeneration by deciding to limit grazing during crucial times next year after buffalo grazing hindered bamboo growth this year. Anticipating future scarcity is reflected in water conservation efforts. Since forest protection has a direct impact on watershed management and long-term water security, the gram sabha (village council) made water conservation its top priority. Many initiatives are infused with intergenerational thinking. The revival of fruit forests is specifically intended to help "coming generations," and the conservation of medicinal plants guarantees that future generations of community members will have access to traditional knowledge and medical resources. The Forest Rights Act is arguably the community's most important response to challenges that are expected to arise in the future. They have established formal rights and mapped 590 acres of forest land for 18 households, providing legal protection against future policy changes or encroachment.

Local motivations based on community solidarity, immediate threat response, and future planning can drive powerful environmental change, as demonstrated by this amazing conservation story, in which community members went from being forest exploiters to forest protectors. Their strategy demonstrates that strong community foundations are frequently the first step towards effective environmental protection, providing important lessons for conservation efforts around the world.

4.3 Ganjam

Preserving a Sense of Community

In Ganjam, communities hold a deep sense of identity that is closely tied to the coast, the sea, their resources, and fishing occupations. Yet, traditional knowledge and practices are gradually eroding with the advance of modernisation and mechanisation in the fisheries sector. Added to this are growing uncertainties and economic vulnerabilities that have shifted aspirations - migration has increased, and younger generations are opting for education and jobs outside fishing. Despite these changes, strong values of ownership, stewardship, and collective responsibility continue to shape community life. This is evident in the way people engage with their land and sea, reflecting a shared commitment to protecting resources. Their involvement in processes such as commons mapping under CRZ regulations demonstrates how these values translate into action. Such efforts not only integrate diverse knowledge systems but also reinforce community rights over coastal spaces. Thus, the motivation to preserve a strong sense of community rooted in culture and tradition is reflected in their efforts to adopt conservation-oriented strategies like commons mapping.

Response to Existing Threats and Vulnerabilities

The coast is highly vulnerable to recurrent cyclones, flooding, and shoreline erosion. According to a key informant, sand mining has further intensified erosion, directly threatening fishing grounds and settlements. At the same time, declining fish availability, increasing mechanisation of fishing vessels, restrictions on fishing days due to climate risks, and regulatory bans have all placed mounting pressure on livelihoods. These uncertainties have driven many, especially the youth, to seek wage labour outside fishing. Faced with encroachment by more powerful actors and the erosion of traditional rights, the community has turned to commons mapping as a collective response. Here, conservation-oriented behaviour is motivated by the need

to safeguard livelihoods and reclaim control over coastal and marine resources in the face of pressing vulnerabilities.

Response to Anticipated Future Threats

Looking ahead, communities anticipate even greater challenges, including displacement and resource loss from sea-level rise, climate variability, and erratic rainfall—once spread across 120 monsoon days, but now compressed into shorter, more intense bursts. External pressures, such as encroachment from development projects like peri-urban waste plants, further heighten these fears. In this context, commons mapping has emerged as a powerful tool that documents community ties to coastal areas and secures rights over traditional spaces, including ecologically sensitive sites like the Olive Ridley turtle nesting beaches that require undisturbed sandy shores. Alongside land and sea rights, education and supplementary livelihoods are increasingly viewed as essential pathways for future security, particularly for younger generations. Continued engagement with policy frameworks such as CRZ regulations reflects the community's adaptive response to anticipated risks. The motivation here lies in ensuring long-term resilience by linking cultural identity and ecological stewardship with proactive conservation and co-management strategies.

5. Abstract Conceptualization

To properly understand how protecting the environment and raising people's awareness are linked, we need a framework that goes beyond typical beliefs about psychology and the environment. This working paper examines the role of motivation in environmental preservation through community change, utilizing three primary theories: ecopsychology, transpersonal social involvement, and community vitality and Elinor Ostrom's ideas on collective resource governance.

Ecopsychology, which recognizes the basic relationship between human mental health and ecological health (Davis & Canty, 2013), is the most relevant subject for understanding our results. This discipline posits that contemporary disconnection from nature engenders both individual and global environmental issues. According to Davis and Canty (2013), the primary notion underpinning ecopsychology is that there is a connection between humans and nature that goes beyond what we can see. This theory helps us comprehend how being conscious of the environment can lead to big changes in the community, and vice-versa.

Transpersonal social engagement is how local communities show that they are aware of more than just people, families, and plants and animals. It builds on this ecological framework. This makes the group as a whole work better than usual means of organizing society would (Rothberg & Coder, 2013). This transpersonal dimension manifests when communities perceive their identity as intricately connected to their ecological context. People who do this feel like they are part of a group with a shared objective, and they realize that their own health is linked to the health of the whole living system.

This focus on the wider picture helps communities stay strong, which is good for their health, which is what makes the difference between just living and genuinely thriving. Dale et al. (2014) used Maslow's hierarchy of needs to think about what keeps a community alive. They claimed that in healthy communities, basic needs like safety and food are fulfilled first, and subsequently higher-level needs like self-actualization and transcendence are met. At the very least, important communities ensure there is enough housing, food security, clean air, and water. Before individuals can reach self-actualization and transcendence, they need to meet their safety, belonging, and respect demands. This is when children keep growing better, have chances to study, enjoy art, and exchange ideas that make a difference in other communities.

Ostrom's commons theory (1990) adds to this by highlighting how institutional arrangements and shared rules can enable communities to govern resources collectively, fostering responsibility, ownership, and long-term sustainability.

Putting these theoretical pieces together gives us a good idea of how certain motivations can act as drivers for ecological preservation through community transformation. This holistic paradigm posits that enduring environmental action is derived from collectives of individuals who have matured mentally, socially, and spiritually to comprehend their intrinsic connection to nature and to act from this profound understanding of their identity (Swan, 2010). The framework provides a lens through which to examine observations from communities that have addressed environmental challenges while and through maintaining their social cohesion and cultural vibrancy. It also helps us understand what drives people to make these kinds of adjustments. This holistic paradigm shows that enduring environmental action is not only ecological but also psychological, social, cultural, and institutional, rooted in motivations that sustain community-led conservation.

6. Discussion

6.1 Preserving a Sense of Community

Taking a communal oath in front of Mother Kalijai in Mangalajodi made protecting birds a religious duty. This gave former hunters and poachers a new reason to work together. This spiritual reframing illustrates how heightened awareness can recalibrate individual tendencies toward the collective good (Rothberg & Coder, 2013). In Uparadikiri, involvement in the Thenga Pali guardianship council and donations to the *Chuli* fund improved relationships within the community, showing how communities incorporate stewardship into their identity (Dale et al., 2014). In Ganjam, collaborative mapping of coastal commons enabled fishermen to regain control over shoreline resources, demonstrating how a robust sense of "we" can enhance social cohesion and promote collective management of shared environments (Rothberg & Coder, 2013).

6.2 Response to existing threats

Taking care of environmental problems sped up work at all sites. A lot of birds died because of the Wildlife Protection Act of 1972. To make up for this, the people of Mangalajodi turned their old fishing boats into eco-tourism boats that took guests on guided tours of nests, eggs, and groups of birds that were moving. This change shows that linking mental health to environmental health can turn a crisis into an opportunity (Davis & Canty, 2013). In Uparadikiri, community-led wildfire patrols and forest mapping arose in response to illegal logging, protecting biodiversity and demonstrating collective efficacy when communities directly confront ecological degradation. In Ganjam, repeated cyclones and the erosion of the shoreline led to the creation of zoning maps based on rights. Villagers used these maps to talk to the government, which made them stronger. This shows that groups that are motivated can turn threats into ways to stay strong.

6.3 Response to anticipated threats

Each community also showed that they could see problems coming and get ready for them. Mangalajodi's method of splitting money from tours between homes, maintenance, and conservation creates long-term incentives and connections between generations. It's clear that stewardship ideas are passed down from father to son through the father-son guide duos (Dale et al., 2014). In Uparadikiri, the creation of nurseries for medicinal plants and efforts to revitalize bamboo meet expected healthcare and habitat requirements, demonstrating human adaptability in response to environmental understanding (Fox, 1990). People in

Ganjam are talking about new ways to make a living, like seafood processing cooperatives and making handicrafts. These are examples of proactive ways to protect against having to move because of climate change. These proactive approaches show how communities can build paths that last longer than just survival when people are worried about the future and their current needs.

6.4 Integrated discussion

The idea of a sense of community- a psychological underpinning that binds people together via a common identity, membership, and purpose- lays the groundwork for community-driven preservation. This motivating factor shows up as improved social cohesion, where locals form stronger emotional bonds with their surroundings and neighbours, creating the social fabric required for long-term preservation initiatives. The social capital necessary for long-term change is produced when a sense of community establishes a framework of shared responsibility where personal incentives coincide with group objectives. The second crucial motivating theme is Response to existing threats, where communities come together in the face of imminent threats to their prized possessions. Communities are compelled to organize protective measures through collective efficacy when they directly witness environmental degradation, cultural loss, or social disruption. These threat-responsive incentives foster a sense of urgency and unity, converting personal worries into concerted community action that employs cooperative tactics to confront current threats. Communities' proactive approach to possible future hazards is reflected in the third theme, response to anticipated threats. Preventive collective action, in which communities unite around common concerns about what might happen rather than what has already happened, is made possible by this forward-looking motivation. To strengthen preservation efforts before crises, arise, communities are encouraged to develop adaptive capacities through anticipatory motivations, which in turn create sustainable frameworks for long-term community transformation.

Together, these three motivational factors provide the social and psychological framework required for successful community transformation, laying the groundwork for preservation initiatives to take root and persist.

7. Conclusions

These narratives centre around the main idea that motivations drive ecological preservation through community transformation: when communities use intrinsic motivations that connect psychological, social, and spiritual dimensions, they become the architects of their own ecological destinies.

The following represents our attempt to create a taxonomy of motivations as drivers:

Preserving a Sense of Community

- Shared Identity
- Cultural Continuity
- Collective Rights
- Collective Action
- Cultural and Religious Practices
- Safeguarding Traditions

Response to Existing Threats and Vulnerabilities

- Livelihood
- Food Security

- Resource Depletion
- Encroachment and Marginalization
- Legal Pressures
- Displacement

Response to Anticipated Future Threats

- Intergenerational Planning
- Building Economic Resilience
- Climate Change
- Long-Term Health and Resource Security
- Adaptive Co-Management

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Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in an its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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